

Synthesis and Reactions of Some Acyl Azides Bearing Phosphorus Substituents

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p-(Diphenylphosphino) benzoyl azide (IIa) and diphenylphosphinoacetyl azide (IIb) are prepared by the action of NaNO₂ and HCl on the corresponding acid hydrazides (I). The azides (II) are subjected to both base- and acid-catalyzed decompositions. II reacts with hydrazine hydrate to give the precursor acid hydrazides (I). The reaction of II with benzylamine affords the corresponding amides (III). When II are allowed to react with anhydrous AlCl₃ in benzene, toluene or anisole, the corresponding anilides (IV) are obtained. The structures of the products are discussed in the light of their chemical and spectroscopic properties.

p-(Diphenylphosphino) benzoic acid hydrazide¹ (Ia) and diphenylphosphinoacetic acid hydrazide² (Ib) were recently prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate on the corresponding esters. In this investigation, we report the conversion of these hydrazides into the corresponding azides with a study of the resulting phosphorus containing acyl azides.

The hydrazide-azide route reported^{3,4} for the conversion of acid hydrazides into the corresponding acyl azides (treatment with NaNO₂ and HCl) is applied to the above hydrazides (I), whereby the corresponding azides (II) are obtained. The structure of II is based upon: (i) analytical data, (ii) the ir spectra of these compounds showing bands⁵ at 2150 cm⁻¹ (azido group) and 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), and (iii) the reactions carried out on them.

The azides (II) were subjected to both base- and acid-catalyzed decompositions. II react with hydrazine hydrate to give the precursors acid hydrazides (I), whose formation is confirmed by direct comparison of m. p. and mixed m. p. When decomposition of the azides (II) is effected with benzylamine, the corresponding N-benzylamides (III) are obtained.

The ir spectra of these products show ν_{max} at 3250-3300 cm⁻¹ (NH) and 1660 cm⁻¹ (amide C=O). Furthermore, the electronic spectra of these compounds show similarity (Table I). The formation of I and III may be represented by the following scheme,

Under Friedel-Crafts conditions, II react with benzene, toluene or anisole with the formation of the corresponding anilides (IV).

The structure of these products is inferred from, (i) analytical data, (ii) the ir spectra of these products showing $\nu_{\max}$ at 3200 (NH) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O), (iii) similarity of the electronic spectra of these products (Table 1), and (iv) the reported⁶ conversion of benzazide to the corresponding anilides under similar conditions.

The conversion of the azides (II) into the corresponding anilides (IV) might involve the intermediate formation of the isocyanate, [R-N=C=O], and the reaction may be represented by the following scheme.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE AMIDES (III) AND ANILIDES (IV)

Compound	m. p. °C	Formula	N%* Found (Calcd.)	UV Spectra	
				$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	log ϵ
IIIa	229-31 [†]	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₃ P	3.32 (3.41)	265 273	3.75 3.54
IIIb	208-10 [†]	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ NO ₃ P	3.89 (4.01)	260 273	2.90 2.84
IVa	224-26 [§]	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₃ P	3.67 (3.53)	277 277	4.50 4.50
IVb	240-42 [§]	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₃ P	3.29 (3.41)	277 277	4.48 4.48
IVc	229-30 [§]	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ NO ₃ P	3.17 (3.28)	287 287	4.47 4.47
IVd	217-18 [§]	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ NO ₃ P	4.37 (4.18)	265 272	3.35 3.19
IVe	204-5 [§]	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ NO ₃ P	4.18 (4.01)	265 272	3.34 3.18
IVf	192-94 [§]	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ NO ₃ P	3.95 (3.83)	265 272	3.30 3.24

* All compounds gave satisfactory analyses for C, H; yields were 70-85%.

[†] Crystallized from ethanol.

[§] Crystallized from benzene.

Experimental

Melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP-1200 using

KBr-wafer technique. Electronic spectra were measured on a Unicam SP-8000 spectrophotometer using ethyl alcohol solutions. *p*-(Diphenylphosphino) benzoic acid hydrazide¹ and diphenylphosphinoacetic acid hydrazide² were prepared according to the known procedures.

p-(Diphenylphosphino) benzoyl azide (IIa) and diphenylphosphinoacetyl azide (IIb): To a suspension of the hydrazide (Ia) or (Ib) in HCl (2.0 g; 1 N, 100 ml) at 5°, a cold sodium nitrite solution was added dropwise with stirring. After complete addition, the reaction mixture was left at room temp. for 1 h. The product obtained was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. IIa was obtained as a brown oil (85%) which could not be solidified. (Found: C, 65.87; H, 3.99; N, 12.35. C₁₉H₁₄N₃O₂P requires C, 66.15; H, 4.04; N, 12.10%). $\nu_{\max}$ 2150 (N₃), 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O). (IIb) was recrystallized (80%) from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colourless crystals, m.p. 85-6° (decomp.). (Found: C, 58.65; H, 4.11; N, 14.45. C₁₄H₁₂N₃O₂P requires C, 58.94; H, 4.21; N, 14.77%); $\nu_{\max}$ 2100 (N₃), 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Reaction of II with hydrazine hydrate: To a solution of the azide (II) (0.1 mol) in 200 ml dry benzene, hydrazine hydrate (0.3 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1h, after which excess benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The product obtained was recrystallized from ethanol in colourless crystals (75%). The product was found in each case by mixed m.p. to be the acid hydrazide (I).

Reaction of II with benzylamine: The reaction was carried out as described above and the product obtained (III) was recrystallized from the suitable solvent (Table 1).

Reaction of II with anhydrous AlCl₃ in benzene, toluene or anisole: To a stirred mixture of anhydrous AlCl₃ in dry benzene, toluene or anisole (0.3 mol; 100 ml), a solution of the azide (II) in the same dry hydrocarbon (0.1 mol; 100 ml) was added dropwise. After complete addition, the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h. The complex was decomposed with ice-cooled hydrochloric acid (15%) and then steam distilled to remove the excess hydrocarbon. The solid obtained was filtered off, washed thoroughly with water and recrystallized from the suitable solvent (Table 1).

References

- M. EL-DEBK, M. A. HASSAN and S. EL-HAMSHARY, *Ain Shams Sci. Bull.*, 1977, 21A, 176.
- S. M. KIROVA, G. P. (1977), DA-18150.
- M. VANGHELOVICI and I. MOISE, *Bull. Chem. Pura appl.* (1941-1942) 3a, 885, 106 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1944, 38, 5500).
- The Chemistry of Penicillin, Princeton Univ. Press, Princeton, N.J., 1949, p. 788.
- L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley, New York, 1960, p. 274.
- E. FAHR, L. NEWMANN and J. LIEBIGES, *Ann. Chem.*, 1969, 721, 14.